

Conceptual and theoretical frameworks of educational
digitalisation in primary and secondary education.

A scoping review.

Telmo Arriazu Muñoz

David Recio Moreno

Alicia Peñalva Vélez

Universidad Pública de Navarra

Protocol-ScR V.2

Introduction

Rationale

The purpose of this scoping review is to analyse the conceptualisation of digitalisation in the field of formal education. This study is justified by the need to clarify this concept within a broader framework of educational innovation, given that digitalisation has established itself as a central phenomenon in the transformation of educational systems worldwide.

It also seeks to identify the main dimensions and theoretical approaches used to conceptualise this process in the educational context, with the aim of contributing to a more precise understanding and a more effective application in pedagogical practice.

Objectives

General objective

- To map and analyse the conceptualisations of educational digitalisation and the theoretical frameworks proposed in the academic literature published between 2015 and 2025 in the context of formal education at primary and secondary levels.

Specific objectives

- **Identify** explicit and implicit definitions of educational digitalisation present in the literature.
- **Describe** the dimensions, analytical categories and components associated with the concept.
- **Examine** the theoretical frameworks and conceptual approaches underpinning these conceptualisations.
- **Analyse** convergences, divergences and terminological ambiguities (for example, distinctions between digitalisation, educational digitalisation, digital transformation, etc., if they appear in the corpus).
- **Explore** how digitalisation is articulated with other relevant constructs in formal education.
- **Identify** conceptual gaps and emerging areas that require further theoretical development.

Methods

Research Question

The research question motivating this scoping review is the following: **How has educational digitalisation been conceptualised and what theoretical frameworks have been proposed in the academic literature between 2015 and 2025 within formal education at primary and secondary levels?**

Eligibility Criteria

The eligibility criteria were defined in coherence with the research question and following methodological recommendations for scoping reviews, in order to ensure consistency between the research question and the study selection process.

Inclusion

Studies meeting the following criteria were included:

- Peer-reviewed scientific articles.
- Systematic literature reviews.
- Publications between 2015 and 2025 (inclusive).
- Research explicitly focused on the conceptualisation of educational digitalisation or on the development of theoretical frameworks related to the integration of digital technologies in education, provided they include conceptual development.
- Studies situated within the field of formal education, corresponding to primary and secondary education levels.
- Publications in Spanish or English.

Exclusion

The following were excluded:

- Publications not subject to peer review, books, book chapters, or conference proceedings.
- Publications prior to 2015.
- Studies focused on non-formal or informal educational contexts, as well as research on digitalisation in non-educational sectors.

- Works that mention digitalisation only tangentially without conceptual or theoretical development, and studies focused exclusively on technological tools or technical implementation without conceptual analysis. That is, implementations or considerations of specific digital technologies were not taken into account.
- Studies not situated within the field of formal education, corresponding to primary and secondary education levels.
- Documents for which full text was unavailable after exhaustive searching.

Information Sources

The bibliographic search was conducted in the following electronic databases:

- Scopus
- Web of Science Core Collection (WoS)
- ERIC (Education Resources Information Center)
- Dialnet

Search Strategies

The search strategy was constructed by directly translating the research question into three conceptual blocks combined using Boolean logic: educational digitalisation (Block A), theoretical and conceptual frameworks (Block B) and formal education at primary and secondary levels (Block C). Within each block, terms are combined with OR, while blocks are articulated with each other using AND, so that each retrieved result must contain at least one term from each of the three blocks.

In Block A, the terms digitalization, digitalisation and digitization are combined given their polysemic nature. The remaining terms in the block — digital transformation, educational technology, digital learning and digital education — implicitly incorporate the educational context.

In Block B, the terms framework and model were restricted using AND (conceptual* OR theoretical) to avoid retrieving references to technical, statistical or business frameworks; the terms conceptualization and theorization were included without additional restriction as they inherently imply theoretical work.

In Block C, the most specific terms of institutionalised formal education were prioritised: curriculum, K-12, elementary school, elementary education, primary school and secondary school.

The search was executed in Scopus, WOS and ERIC with queries in English. In Dialnet the descriptors were adapted to Spanish while maintaining the same three-block structure.

Table 1. Search strategy: Scopus and Web of Science

Block	Search query	Filters
A	digitalization OR digitalisation OR digitization OR "digital transformation" OR "educational technology" OR "digital learning" OR "digital education"	
B	(framework* AND (conceptual* OR theoretical)) OR (model* AND (conceptual* OR theoretical)) OR conceptualization OR theorization	
C	curricul* OR K-12 OR "elementary school" OR "elementary educat*" OR "primary school" OR "secondary school"	

Table 2. Search strategy: ERIC

Block	Search query	Filters
A	(title:digitalization OR title:digitalisation OR title:digitization OR title:digitisation OR title:"digital transformation" OR title:"educational technology" OR title:"digital learning" OR title:"digital education" OR abstract:digitalization OR abstract:digitalisation OR abstract:digitization OR abstract:digitisation OR abstract:"digital transformation" OR abstract:"educational technology" OR abstract:"digital learning" OR abstract:"digital education")	
B	(title:framework OR title:frameworks OR title:model OR title:models OR title:conceptualization OR title:conceptualisation OR title:theorization OR title:theorisation OR title:theoretical OR title:conceptual OR abstract:framework OR abstract:frameworks OR abstract:model OR abstract:models OR abstract:conceptualization OR abstract:conceptualisation OR abstract:theorization OR abstract:theorisation OR abstract:theoretical OR abstract:conceptual)	
C	(title:curricul* OR title:K-12 OR title:"elementary school" OR title:"primary school" OR title:"secondary school" OR abstract:curricul* OR abstract:K-12 OR abstract:"elementary school" OR abstract:"primary school" OR abstract:"secondary school")	

Table 3. Search strategy: Dialnet

Block	Search query	Filters
A+B+C	(digitalización OR "transformación digital" OR "tecnología educativa" OR "educación digital" OR "aprendizaje digital") AND ("marco conceptual" OR "marco teórico" OR conceptualización OR teorización) AND (curricul* OR "educación básica" OR "educación primaria" OR "educación secundaria")	

Data Management

Zotero will be used as the reference manager to:

- Import and centralise search results from all consulted databases.
- Identify and eliminate duplicate records automatically and manually.
- Organise and store studies throughout the different phases of the review.

The **initial screening** by title and abstract will be conducted using CribaDoc (Arriazu Muñoz & Arriazu Muñoz, 2026), an open-source self-developed software (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.19241992), which will allow:

- Classifying each record according to a binary decision: "include" or "exclude".
- Systematically recording the specific reason for exclusion for each discarded study.
- Incorporating observations or comments on records presenting doubts or ambiguities.
- Flagging studies requiring full-text review to determine final eligibility.

Predefined Data Extraction and Analysis Schemes

Data extraction will be carried out using a structured template whose items are specified in the Data items section.

The analysis will combine a descriptive approach (temporal, geographical and methodological distribution) with an inductively driven thematic categorisation, aimed at identifying patterns in the conceptualisation of educational digitalisation.

Data items

In order to ensure systematic extraction consistent with the review objectives, a structured data collection template will be used. The variables to be extracted are organised into the following categories:

Category	Variable (item to extract)
Bibliographic data	Authorship
	Year of publication
	Journal or publication source
	Country or region of study
Study characteristics	Document type
	Methodological design
	Educational level analysed
	Scope: Administration, educational institution and classroom.
Conceptual dimension	Explicit definition of educational digitalisation
	Terms related to educational digitalisation
	Identified dimensions (technological, pedagogical, organisational, curricular, political, etc.)
Contextual information	Theoretical framework or conceptual model used
	Temporal period of the study
	Explicit mention of the COVID-19 context

The conceptual variables will allow identification of patterns, convergences, divergences and ambiguities in the conceptualisation of educational digitalisation. The template may be iteratively adjusted if relevant categories emerge that were not initially anticipated.

Risk of Bias in Individual Studies

In keeping with the exploratory nature of scoping reviews, no formal assessment of risk of bias will be carried out using standardised instruments. During the synthesis, the theoretical approaches and paradigmatic positions of the studies will be considered as contextual elements for interpreting the conceptual diversity identified.

Data

Synthesis

Data synthesis will combine three complementary strategies:

1. **Structured extraction tables:** The variables defined in the Data items section

will be systematised, allowing visualisation of temporal, geographical and thematic distribution patterns.

2. **Graphical representations:** Descriptive charts will be used to show trends in scientific output (distribution by year, country, educational level and methodological approach).
3. **Analytical narrative synthesis:** Convergences, divergences and conceptual recurrences in the definition of educational digitalisation and its associated theoretical frameworks will be identified and described.

The synthesis will be descriptive and cartographic in nature, without evaluative or meta-analytical purposes, in keeping with the objectives of a scoping review.

References

Arriazu Muñoz, T. y Arriazu Muñoz, J. (2026). *CribaDoc* (v0.2.0) [Software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19241992>